

Comparative study of seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average and Holt–Winters modeling for forecasting monthly ground-level ozone

Cite as: AIP Advances 13, 035303 (2023); <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0132812>

Submitted: 31 October 2022 • Accepted: 04 February 2023 • Published Online: 01 March 2023

 Abdu Mohammed Seid, et al.

View Online

Export Citation

CrossMark

APL Machine Learning
Machine Learning for Applied Physics
Applied Physics for Machine Learning

**First Articles
Now Online!**

Comparative study of seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average and Holt–Winters modeling for forecasting monthly ground-level ozone

Cite as: AIP Advances 13, 035303 (2023); doi: 10.1063/5.0132812

Submitted: 31 October 2022 • Accepted: 4 February 2023 •

Published Online: 1 March 2023

View Online

Export Citation

CrossMark

Abebaw Bizuneh Alemu,^{1,2,a)} and Bayile Damtie¹

AFFILIATIONS

¹ Department of Physics, College of Science, Bahir Dar University, P. O. Box 79, Bahir Dar, Ethiopia

² Ethiopian Institute of Textile and Fashion Technology, P. O. Box 79, Bahir Dar, Ethiopia

³ Department of Mathematics, College of Science, Bahir Dar University, P. O. Box 79, Bahir Dar, Ethiopia

^{a)} Author to whom correspondence should be addressed: abebaw08@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this study, ground-level ozone is modeled using Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA) and additive Holt–Winters models over the North-Western cluster of Ethiopia using four homogeneous series of more than 13 years of data from the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts. We split the dataset into training and testing sets. We used the data during the period 2007–2019 for model formulation and parameter estimation and the one year data in 2020 to test model forecasts. More than 60 SARIMA models have been generated for the time series. The goodness of fit of these models has been assessed using the Akaike information criterion and Bayesian information criterion. After rigorous assessment, the seasonal ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)[12], ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12], ARIMA(0,1,2)(0,0,2)[12], and ARIMA(2,0,0)(2,1,0)[12] models have been identified as best predictive models for Addis Ababa, Ras Dashen, Danakil Depression, and Bahir Dar, respectively. We applied model evaluation metrics, such as root mean square error, mean absolute error, and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) to compare the accuracy between seasonal ARIMA and Holt–Winters models. Among the SARIMA and Holt–Winters models, our findings show that the best model for forecasting surface-level ozone is ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)[12] and ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12] for Addis Ababa and Ras Dashen stations, respectively. However, for Danakil Depression and Bahir Dar stations, the Holt–Winters model with $\alpha = 0.346$, $\beta = 0.023$, $\gamma = 0.36$ and $\alpha = 0.302$, $\beta = 0.019$, $\gamma = 0.266$, respectively, are found to be best models than the SARIMA. Moreover, the maximum MAPE were found to be less than 7.86% in the study, and hence all the forecasts are acceptable.

© 2023 Author(s). All article content, except where otherwise noted, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0132812>

I. INTRODUCTION

Ground-level ozone (GLO), also known as surface-level ozone and tropospheric ozone, becomes one of the critical concerns over the world. A high level of surface ozone concentrations can damage the human respiratory system, organs, immune systems and tissues, and even sometimes threaten human life as a major air pollutant.^{1–5} It also affects the growth of plants by destroying their leaf tissues.^{6–9} In addition to this, ozone is an important greenhouse gas as it protects the Earth from dangerous UV rays from the Sun. Ozone affects climate change, which in turn the climate change influences ozone

concentration through chemical composition, transport, and temperature changes.¹⁰ Moreover, it is a harmful air pollutant and the air quality index tracks ground-level ozone as one of the major air pollutants. The United States Environmental Protection Agency revised the National Ambient Air Quality Standard for ozone on October 1, 2015, from 0.075 to 0.070 ppm, averaged over 8 h. Hence, it requires a real-time climate prediction of O₃ to design future policies on control strategies of O₃ that could support planning for air pollution control.^{2,5}

Accurate modeling of O₃ is important to ensure its exact prediction. Efficient prediction of ground-level ozone is becoming a

necessity for preventing the highly challenging events related to the peak concentration of ozone. Many prediction models use a statistical method as a tool for forecasting future data. In statistical data analysis, there are several methods for statistical prediction, such as regressing analysis, classical decomposition method, Box and Jenkins method, and smoothing techniques. Various statistical methods will give different predictions depending on the range of datasets. These techniques provide predicting models of different accuracy.

In natural situations, the concentration of ozone in any area has a lot of seasonality and trends.^{11–14} Forecasting such cases requires models that will account for the trend and seasonality in the data. One of the most widely applied forecasting techniques that is used to project future values is the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, which is a more generalization of the autoregressive-Moving Average (ARMA) model. The basic assumptions in implementing the ARMA model is the stationarity of the data series. The model combines two different components: Autoregression (AR) and Moving average (MA). The AR part indicates a changing variable that regresses on its prior value; the MA part indicates the dependency between the observation and a residual error. However, in reality, the ozone series may not be stationary always to be best modeled with ARMA. On the other hand, the ARIMA model is useful to model non-stationarity time series. It assumes that the data becomes stationary after differencing, and the Integral (I) part represents the differencing of raw observations to allow for the time series to become stationary. Moreover, for seasonal time series forecasting, scholars in the field proposed a Seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA) model.¹⁵ For instance, Guarnaccia *et al.*¹⁶ implemented ARIMA to predict air pollution in San Nicolas de Garza of Monterrey in Mexico. They used hourly CO concentrations data to estimate ARIMA model parameters and predict future pollution. Their study indicated that the ARIMA model yields reliable prediction on a short time range up to 24 h in the future with a reasonable compromise between precision and the forecast horizon from the hourly data. Kumar *et al.*¹⁷ also used the ARIMA model to obtain maximum daily surface ozone concentration forecasts from hourly surface-level ozone data collected in the period July 1998–March 1999 at the airport in Brunei Darussalam. Their study revealed that the overall model performance was found to be quite satisfactory with normalized mean square error of 0.02 and mean absolute percentage error of 13.14%. Gocheva-Ilieva *et al.*¹⁸ also investigated future concentrations of primary air pollutants, including ground level ozone in the town of Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria, within a 1 year period from September 1, 2011, to August 31, 2012, based on hourly measurements. Their study indicated that the SARIMA models obtained demonstrated very good fitting performance with regard to the observed air pollutants and short-term predictions for 72 h ahead, in particular, in the case of ozone.

Similarly, Holt–Winters' modeling is the other most common time series prediction method that can take into account both the trend and seasonality in the forecasting. It is useful to model the three different components of a time series (i.e., the average or level, trend, and seasonality components of a series). Hence, the Holt–Winters model comprises the level, trend, and seasonality components of a time series together with corresponding parameters called smoothing parameters. In statistical modeling, the models are formulated using a training datasets for estimating model parameters in such a way that the model best fits the training datasets

so that one can use the model to predict future values of the series. In this case, one of the model's predictive performance is usually evaluated using test datasets by implementing different measurement metrics, such as root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE).

Both ARIMA and Holt–Winters models are commonly used in time series analysis in general. To mention some, Syaifei *et al.*¹⁹ implemented both Holt–Winters and ARIMA to predict the concentrations of daily air pollutants in Surabaya, Indonesia, from a 15 days hourly air quality data in 2014, such as particulate (PM₁₀), carbon monoxide (CO), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and ozone (O₃) concentrations. Their finding showed that the Holt–Winters model performed well in forecasting CO, NO₂, and O₃, whereas ARIMA is best in forecasting PH₁₀ and SO₂. In a study conducted by Alonso Brito *et al.*,²⁰ the SARIMA model presented better results than the Holt–Winters month in forecasting monthly streamflow. On the other hand, Omara and Kawamukaia,²¹ in a study about the prediction of normalized difference vegetation index, obtained better results by the method of Holt–Winters. Moreover, Markovska *et al.*²² showed that the ARIMA model gives more accurate results when the prediction is based on daily time-series data, while the Holt–Winters model has better performance for weekly and monthly time series data. Thus, the studies so far indicated that both ARIMA and Holt–Winters models are applicable to forecast future values in time series data, in general, but, there is no general consensus regarding which model is better for which time series data and in what scenario explicitly. It is reasonable to assume from the previous studies that the models performance depends on specific time series data under study. This and literature search insights of null report in the area of ground-level ozone forecast in the Ethiopian context motivated us to investigate ARIMA and Holt–Winters models forecast of ground-level ozone of four selected stations of Ethiopia.

In this study, we modeled the ground-level ozone series of four selected stations (Addis Ababa, Bahir Dar, Ras Dashen, and Danakil Depression) of Ethiopia during the study period by considering trends and seasonality patterns from the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) monthly ground-level ozone data. Particularly, we were interested on seasonal ARIMA and Holt–Winters model forecasts together with corresponding model performance.

The remaining part of the paper is organized as follows: In Sec. II, we discuss the geographical location of the study area. Section III provides information on data description and methodology. Section IV contains the results and discussions of the study. Finally, the conclusions of the study are forwarded.

II. STUDY AREA

We are interested to investigate the concentration of ground-level ozone over the North-Western cluster of Ethiopia.¹¹ It is found in the North-Eastern part of Africa, which lies approximately between 9.5°N and 14.5°N latitude and 32.5°E and 40.5°E longitude. The motivation for this specific study area in Ethiopia arises from a study report by Alemu *et al.*¹¹ that indicates the existence of a high overall mean total column ozone (TCO) concentration over the North-Western part of Ethiopia and a low concentration over the Southern part of Ethiopia. We would like to see the ground-level

FIG. 1. The location of North-Western cluster of Ethiopia.

TABLE I. Geographical location and elevation of stations.

Station code	Longitude (deg)	Latitude (deg)	Altitude
AA	38.74	9.03	2355
RD	38.37	13.24	4550
DK	40.30	14.24	-125
BD	37.36	11.57	1800

ozone time series contributions to the high overall mean TCO in the study area considered bearing in mind that low ground-level ozone and high TCO is useful to life on Earth. The topography of the study area considered is highly diverse, including the extreme points of Ethiopia, with an elevation ranging from -125 m at the Danakil Depression, which is the hottest place on earth to 4620 m at Ras-Dashen mountain.^{23,24} These variations in topography might also have an impact on the distribution of surface level ozone and its forecast. The current study is thus to model the status of surface level ozone over the selected four stations—Addis Ababa (AA), Ras Dashen (RD), Danakil Depression (DK), and Bahir Dar (BD) as shown in Fig. 1 (corresponding topographic details are given in Table I)—and to forecast it with corresponding model performance check.

III. DATA DESCRIPTION AND METHODOLOGY

In this work, we utilized ground-level ozone data from the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) from November 2007–December 2020. We split the data into two parts: the first part of data (November 2007–December 2019) is used for model formulation and parameter estimation and the last year's data (January 1, 2020–December 31, 2020) is used for model validation.

A. Seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average (SARIMA) modeling

Forecasting is a time-series projection of future events based on current and historical data.²⁵ For time series data, there are several different prediction methods. Among the effective approaches for analyzing time series data, ARIMA modeling is one of the most widely used methods for data with both seasonal patterns and trends. The ARIMA model has been used to forecast the mid- and long-term concentration of ozone over many study areas.^{26,27}

The ARIMA model can be thought as a model that combines three different time series models: Auto-regression (AR), Integrated (I), and Moving average (MA) models. The AR part of ARIMA indicates the change of a variable that regresses on some of its prior values, the MA part indicates the dependency between an observation and a residual error, and the I part represents the differencing of raw observations to allow for the time series to become stationary. ARIMA models can be denoted by ARIMA(p,d,q), where p is the order of time lag of the autoregressive model, d is the degree of differencing, and q is the order of the moving average model.

An autoregressive (AR) model of order p is the one in which the current observation x_t is regressed on previous observations $x_{t-1}, x_{t-2}, \dots, x_{t-p}$ of the same time series. This can be expressed mathematically as

$$x_t = \xi + \phi_1 x_{t-1} + \phi_2 x_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p x_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t, \quad (1)$$

where $\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_p$ represents the regression coefficients, ξ is the constant term, and ε_t is the random error. Taking the ϕ terms to the left-hand side reduces Eq. (1) in to

$$x_t - \phi_1 x_{t-1} - \phi_2 x_{t-2} - \dots - \phi_p x_{t-p} = \xi + \varepsilon_t.$$

If B denotes the backward shift operator such that $Bx_t = x_{t-1}$, $Bx_{t-1} = x_{t-2}$, and so on, Eq. (1) can be written as

$$(1 - \phi_1 B - \phi_2 B^2 - \dots - \phi_p B^p)x_t = \xi + \varepsilon_t. \quad (2)$$

Replacing x_t by its deviation (\bar{x}_t) from the mean μ , the equation becomes

$$\phi_p(B)\bar{x}_t = \varepsilon_t, \quad (3)$$

where $\phi_p(B) = 1 - \phi_1 B - \phi_2 B^2 - \dots - \phi_p B^p$, and $\bar{x}_t = x_t - \mu$.

Similarly, a moving average (MA) model of order q can be defined in terms of the random error terms as

$$x_t = \mu + \rho_t - \theta_1 \rho_{t-1} - \theta_2 \rho_{t-2} - \dots - \theta_q \rho_{t-q}. \quad (4)$$

In terms of the backward shift operator B , a moving average model of order q can be expressed as

$$x_t = \mu + (1 - \theta_1 B - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_q B^q)\rho_t \quad (5)$$

or

$$x_t = \mu + \theta_q(B)\rho_t,$$

where $\theta_q(B) = 1 - \theta_1 B - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_q B^q$.

The two models AR(p) and MA(q) can be combined to form a mixed Autoregressive Moving Average, ARMA(p, q), model for a stationary time series that is represented by Eq. (7),

$$\phi_p(B)x_t = \xi + \theta_q(B)\rho_t, \tag{6}$$

$$y_t = \xi + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i y_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^q \theta_j \varepsilon_{t-j}, \tag{7}$$

where y_t is the observed ground-level ozone value at time t ; ξ is a constant; i and j are the autoregressive and moving average process lags, respectively; ϕ_i is the autoregressive coefficient at lag i ; θ_j is the moving average coefficient at lag j ; p and q are the autoregressive and moving average orders, respectively.

These models are applicable to a stationary time series. If the time series is non-stationary, it needs first to be transformed into a stationary time series by a process called differencing, in which the previous observation x_{t-1} is subtracted from the current observation x_t . The differencing can be performed with the help of a difference operator ∇ defined as

$$\nabla^d x_t = \nabla(\nabla^{d-1} x_t). \tag{8}$$

Combining the three techniques (autoregressive model, moving average model, and differencing), an ARIMA model is generated. A general ARIMA model of order (p, d, q) representing a time series can be expressed as

$$\phi(B)\nabla^d x_t = \theta(B)\rho_t. \tag{9}$$

In the context of the present study, x_t and ρ_t represent the surface ozone level and random error terms at time t , respectively, while d represents the order of differencing.

Seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA) is an extension of ARIMA that includes an additional seasonal term. Seasonality can be defined as a pattern of repeating itself over a fixed time interval.²⁸ In addition to ARIMA, there will be four additional elements in SARIMA that corresponds to orders corresponding to the seasonal elements. The ground-level ozone can be modeled using SARIMA model with order (p, d, q)(P, D, Q)[s], where P, D, and Q are order of seasonal AR polynomial function, order of seasonal MA polynomial function, and order of seasonal differencing, respectively, for period of the season s . The general equation can be written as²⁹

$$\Phi(L^s)\phi(L)(1-L)^d(1-L^s)^D y_t = \Theta(L^s)\theta(L)\varepsilon_t, \tag{10}$$

where L is the lag operator, $\phi(L)$ is the autoregressive polynomial function of order p , $\theta(L)$ is the moving average polynomial function of order q , $\Phi(L^s)$ is the seasonal autoregressive polynomial function of order P , $\Theta(L^s)$ is the seasonal moving average polynomial function of order Q , d is the differencing order, D is the seasonal differencing order, and ε_t must be normally distributed, not autocorrelated and homoscedastic error term.

B. Holt-Winters modeling

Holt-Winters modeling is also the most widely used method for time series data with both trend and seasonal patterns. The

method comprises of forecast and smoothing equations for level, trend, and seasonal components with corresponding smoothing parameters α , β , and γ , respectively. It is a method of forecasting that applies exponential smoothing technique to the seasonal component in addition to the level and trends.^{30,31} Due to its accuracy in prediction, the Holt-Winters model has been widely used in many fields. Dantas *et al.*³² used the Holt-Winters method to forecast air transportation demand. Reizer and Juda-Rezler³³ also used the Holt-Winters model to forecast the daily PM2.5 concentrations.

For the additive Holt-Winters prediction function, the level equation is given by the weighted average between the seasonally adjusted observation and non-seasonal forecast for time t ,

$$L_t = \alpha(y_t - S_{t-s}) + (1 - \alpha)(L_{t-1} + T_{t-1}). \tag{11}$$

The trend equation is given by the weighted average of the estimated trends at time t based on $L_t - L_{t-1}$ and T_{t-1} , the previous estimates of the trend,

$$T_t = \beta(L_t - L_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta)T_{t-1}. \tag{12}$$

The seasonal equation is given by the weighted average between the current seasonal index and the seasonal index of the same season s period ago,

$$S_t = \gamma(y_t - L_t) + (1 - \gamma)S_{t-s}. \tag{13}$$

The forecast equation is given by

$$F_{t+k} = L_t + kT_t + S_{t+k-s}, \tag{14}$$

where s is the length of the seasonal cycle for the parameters (α , β , and γ) are restricted to the range from 0 to 1.

TABLE II. Scale of judgment for model accuracy.

MAPE	Judgment of forecast accuracy
Less than 10%	Highly accurate
11%–20%	Good forecast
21%–50%	Reasonable forecast
More than 50%	Inaccurate forecast

TABLE III. Exploratory data analysis of monthly ground-level ozone (GLO).

Parameters	Stations			
	AA	RD	DK	BD
Mean	9.54	10.6	14.1	9.93
SD	1.79	1.35	1.46	1.23
Median	9.96	10.59	13.97	10.04
CV	19%	13%	10%	12%
Max	17.15	16.20	19.10	12.48
Min	6.10	7.97	10.84	6.92
Kurtosis	4.11	2.29	0.37	−0.51
Skewness	1.26	0.92	0.43	−0.30

FIG. 2. Monthly ground-level ozone (2007–2020).

The time series data are also grouped into two sections: the initial data and testing data. The initial data are the data of two seasonal periods. The initial data are used to obtain the initial value of the base level, trends, and seasonal factors, while the test data are used

to make the process of forecasting with the number of data p . In the test data, the values of the base level, trend, and seasonal factors are calculated for each period. The initial value for the base level is given by

FIG. 3. Annual variation of monthly mean ground-level ozone (2007–2020).

$$L_0 = \frac{1}{h} \sum_{i=0}^h X_i, \tag{15}$$

where h is the number of initial data and X_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, h$ are the initial data. Initial value for the trend (T_0) is given by

$$T_0 = \frac{\bar{X}_{t2} - \bar{X}_{t1}}{m}, \tag{16}$$

where \bar{X}_{t1} is the average of the initial year data, \bar{X}_{t2} is the average of second year data, and m is the number of seasons used in forecasting.

We use R software for model selection and multistep ahead point forecast.

C. Model performance

Goodness of fit is the measure of model accuracy with respect to the observed values or data. We have used Akaike information criterion (AIC) and Bayesian information criterion (BIC) to compare the accuracy of models in the same class of ARIMA models that estimates the relative amount of information lost by a given model under the assumption of independent model errors. In the current study, we used both AIC and BIC to assess the degree of accuracy of the forecasts as proposed by Akaike.³⁴ We define AIC and BIC as follows:

$$AIC = \ln(\sigma_\epsilon^2) + \frac{2(p+q)}{n}, \tag{17}$$

$$BIC = n \ln \sigma_\epsilon^2 + k \ln(n), \tag{18}$$

$$\sigma_\epsilon^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^o - y_i^p)^2,$$

where k is the number of model parameters, p and q are the parameter values, n is the total number of observed data at each station, y_i^o and y_i^p are the observed and predicted values of ground-level ozone at the i th month, respectively.

In addition to this, we have also used mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) for evaluating the performance of different model classes of ARIMA and Holt–Winters models. The mean absolute error (MAE) measures the average magnitude of the errors in a set of forecasts. The root mean square error (RMSE) is a quadratic scoring rule that measures the average magnitude of the error. The difference between the observed and corresponding forecasted values are each squared and then averaged over the sample. It measures the accuracy as a percentage and can be calculated as the average absolute percent error for each period minus the actual values divided by actual values as follows:

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i^o - y_i^p|}{n}, \tag{19}$$

FIG. 4. Autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation function of all the four stations data.

TABLE IV. Best ARIMA model and estimated parameter values of ARIMA model for ground-level ozone (GLO).

Terms	AA		RD		DK		BD	
	ARIMA(2,0,4) (1,1,2)[12]		ARIMA(3,1,0) (2,0,0)[12]		ARIMA(0,1,2) (0,0,2)[12]		ARIMA(2,0,0) (2,1,0)[12]	
	Estimates	Std. error						
AR ₁	-0.093	0.138	-0.510	0.080			0.257	0.087
AR ₂	-0.641	0.209	-0.409	0.082			0.164	0.091
AR ₃			0.410	0.077				
MA ₁	0.323	0.143			-0.574	0.081		
MA ₂	0.883	0.225			-0.348	0.084		
MA ₃	0.159	0.112						
MA ₄	0.419	0.074						
SAR ₁	-0.417	0.180	0.456	0.087			-0.532	0.088
SAR ₂			0.175	0.096			-0.229	0.093
SMA ₁	-0.044	0.199			0.199	0.087		
SMA ₂	-0.682	0.122			0.315	0.085		
Drift	-0.01	0.0048						
AIC	443.46		446.89		465.62		335.94	
BIC	475.17		464.67		480.44		370.36	

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^o - y_i^p)^2}{n}}, \quad (20)$$

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i^o - y_i^p}{y_i^o} \right|, \quad (21)$$

FIG. 5. Seasonal ARIMA model: actual and predicted data of training sets.

FIG. 6. Holt-Winters model: actual and predicted data of training sets.

where n is the total number of observed data at each station, y_i^o and y_i^p are the observed and predicted values of ground-level ozone at the i th month, respectively.

In order to test model accuracy, different authors used MAPE as a tool.³⁵ We also have used MAPE based on the developed scale of judgment for forecast model accuracy by Lewis³⁶ as shown in Table II.

D. Correlation analysis

The Pearson correlation analysis is made between the actual and forecast values of surface level ozone over each station. We also visualized the monthly and seasonal linear correlation of the model with the actual values. In Eq. (22) below, the value of R is between -1 and 1 . The positive and negative values of R indicates the

FIG. 7. Seasonal ARIMA model: actual and forecasted data of testing sets.

FIG. 8. Holt–Winters model: actual and forecasted data of testing sets.

positive and negative relationships,³⁷ respectively. The correlation R is defined by

$$R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^o - \bar{y}^o)(y_i^p - \bar{y}^p)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^o - \bar{y}^o)^2 (y_i^p - \bar{y}^p)^2}}, \quad (22)$$

where n is the total number of observed data at each station, y_i^o and y_i^p are the observed and predicted values of ground-level ozone on the i th month, and \bar{y}^o and \bar{y}^p are the long-term mean of observed and predicted values, respectively.

IV. RESULTS

The main objective of this paper is to determine a model that gives a more accurate prediction of the ground-level ozone for the North-Western cluster of Ethiopia by comparing the result of the error matrices of ARIMA and additive Holt–Winters models. The methodological procedure for building these models is started from the exploratory data analysis as follows:

From the exploratory data analysis of Table III, the values of kurtosis at Danakil Depression and Bahir Dar stations are in between -2 and $+2$, it can be considered as an acceptable normally distributed data,³⁸ and on the other hand, we need to transform the data for Addis Ababa and Ras Dashen stations as the corresponding

TABLE V. Error matrices of ARIMA and Holt–Winters models for ground-level ozone (GLO).

Stations	Models	Error matrices		
		RMSE	MAE	MAPE (%)
AA	ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)[12]	1.08	0.77	7.86
	HW $\alpha = 0.187, \beta = 0.036, \gamma = 0.559$	1.37	0.99	10.6
RD	ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12]	1.08	0.82	7.76
	HW $\alpha = 0.366, \beta = 0.025, \gamma = 0.583$	1.10	0.83	7.97
DK	ARIMA(0,1,2)(0,0,2)[12]	1.20	0.97	6.91
	HW $\alpha = 0.346, \beta = 0.023, \gamma = 0.360$	1.17	0.93	6.59
BD	ARIMA(2,0,0)(2,1,0)[12]	0.90	0.69	7.07
	HW $\alpha = 0.302, \beta = 0.019, \gamma = 0.266$	0.85	0.65	6.57

TABLE VI. Estimated parameter values of the Holt–Winters model for ground-level ozone (GLO).

Stations	Estimated of parameters		
	α	β	γ
AA	0.187	0.036	0.559
RD	0.366	0.025	0.583
DK	0.346	0.023	0.360
BD	0.302	0.019	0.266

kurtosis values exceed 2. We give the plots of the monthly ground-level ozone and the annual variation of monthly mean ground-level ozone during the study period from November 2007 to December 2020 in Figs. 2 and 3 to observe the behavior of the time series.

The exploratory analysis in Figs. 2 and 3 indicated the existence of slightly decreasing linear trends over the four stations. In all stations, the data values tend to decrease over time, but the magnitude of the seasonal change remains the same, then the seasonal changes are additive. The patterns of monthly ground-level ozone have similar curved trends with two local peaks of the maximum value in May and October, while the local minimum value was during July. The monthly analysis of ground-level ozone for all stations shows higher variation throughout the study period. In all cases, the peaks were visible at regular intervals, as indicated in Figs. 2 and 3, and the ground-level ozone value over Danakil Depression is significantly higher than the remaining three stations ground-level ozone.

The initial step of SARIMA modeling begins with the check-up of the stationarity of the process. To test the stationarity of

the data, we have applied the ACF and partial autocorrelation function (PACF) charts as shown in Fig. 4, which indicate the values are correlated and nonstationary. This autocorrelation result shows the repetition of patterns over a year. Similarly, we also used the Augmented Dickey–Fuller test (ADF) as proposed by Dobre and Alexandru.³⁹ From the statistical test results of ADF testing H0: the series is not stationary and H1: the series is stationary. Hence, the results become $P = 0.18, 0.31, 0.38,$ and 0.35 for AA, RD, DK, and BD stations, respectively. For all cases, $p > \alpha = 0.05$ indicated that it failed to reject the null hypothesis, and it confirms that all series are not stationary. Hence, we have applied the first difference method to remove both the trend and seasonality of the series. After the implementation of differencing, we also applied the statistical test again, and it confirmed the stationarity of the data.

From the results of ARIMA models, more than 60 seasonal ARIMA models have been generated for the time series. The goodness of fit of such models has been assessed using the Akaike information criterion (AIC) and Bayesian information criterion (BIC). After the exhausting analysis as shown in Table IV, the seasonal ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)[12], ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12], ARIMA(0,1,2)-(0,0,2)[12], and ARIMA(2,0,0)(2,1,0)[12] models have been identified as best predictive models for Addis Ababa, Ras Dashen, Danakil Depression, and Bahir Dar, respectively.

Figures 5 and 6 show that the model fits for the ARIMA and Holt–Winters model, respectively. The figures in both cases indicate that the models formulated using the training dataset describes the data well. Visual inspection of forecasting figures does not show differences in forecasting results clearly as indicated in Figs. 7 and 8. However, the Holt–Winters model does show higher uncertainty on the forecast values.

FIG. 9. The proposed best model data of training sets (actual and predicted).

The comparison of observed and forecasted data was performed using RMSE, MAE, and MAPE to measure the accuracy and efficiency between ARIMA and Holt–Winters models for ground-level ozone forecasting. Tofallis⁴⁰ proposed that the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) is the most accepted measure of prediction for model selection when the data are heteroscedastic. Moreover, the mean absolute percent error (MAPE) expresses the accuracy as a percentage of the error. It can be easier to understand than the other accuracy measures statistics.

Despite the difficulty in identifying the most suitable methods for a particular application,⁴¹ we tried our best to investigate the most efficient technique to forecast the monthly ground-level ozone over our study area. This study compares the seasonal ARIMA and Holt–Winters models to forecast monthly SOL through performance measures. In our case, as can be seen in Table V, the mean absolute percent error (MAPE) of the additive HW model is 10.6%, 7.97%, 6.59%, and 6.57% for the station Addis Ababa, Ras Dashen, Danakil Depression, and Bahir Dar, respectively. Similarly, the mean absolute percent error (MAPE) of the seasonal ARIMA models are 7.86%, 7.76%, 6.91%, and 7.07% for the station Addis Ababa, Ras Dashen, Danakil Depression, and Bahir Dar, respectively. Even if all results were in an acceptable range, our finding leads us to propose the best model for forecasting surface level ozone is ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)[12] and ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12] for Addis Ababa and Ras Dashen stations, respectively, while the Holt–Winters model with ($\alpha = 0.346, \beta = 0.023$ and $\gamma = 0.36$) and ($\alpha = 0.302, \beta = 0.019$ and $\gamma = 0.266$) performed best for Danakil depression and Bahir Dar, respectively, as shown in Table VI.

We applied Pearson correlation analysis between the actual and forecast values of ground-level ozone over each station. We

also visualized the monthly and seasonal linear correlation of the actual and the model values. The result of Fig. 9 showed a strong relationship between the observed and predicted values over all regions. In this regard, we conclude that the two series have similar characteristics.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a univariate approach has been used to forecast the monthly ground-level ozone over the North-Western cluster of Ethiopia. Initially, the exploratory and autocorrelation structure has been analyzed and it reveals the non-stationarity of the data. More than 60 seasonal ARIMA models have been generated based on time series. Goodness of fit of models has been assessed, and the performance of models has been assessed by using Akaike information criterion (AIC) and Bayesian information criterion (BIC). After painstaking analysis, the seasonal ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)-[12], ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)[12], ARIMA(0,1,2)(0,0,2)[12], and ARIMA(2,0,0)(2,1,0)[12] models have been identified as best predictive models for Addis Ababa, Ras Dashen, Danakil Depression, and Bahir Dar, respectively.

We applied error evaluation metrics, such as Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), to compare the accuracy between ARIMA and Holt–Winters models. The accuracies of both model forecasts were tested using the last year's test data (January 1, 2020–December 31, 2020). Our findings lead us to propose the best model for forecasting the ground-level ozone: ARIMA(2,0,4)(1,1,2)12 and ARIMA(3,1,0)(2,0,0)12 for Addis Ababa and Ras Dashen stations, respectively. The Holt–Winters model of $\alpha = 0.346, \beta = 0.023, \gamma = 0.36$ and $\alpha = 0.302, \beta = 0.019, \gamma = 0.266$ is better for Danakil Depression and Bahir Dar stations, respectively.

FIG. 10. ACF and PACF of residual data from the proposed models.

The maximum errors obtained by comparing actual test data with the forecasted model values were less than 7.86%, which is in the acceptable range. Both seasonal ARIMA and Holt–Winters forecasts are very similar and performed well on the test. The SARIMA model seems to perform better than the Holt–Winters model over Addis Ababa and Ras Dashen. On the other hand, the Holt–Winters model showed best results for Danakil Depression and Bahir Dar. The result is in line with Alonso Brito *et al.*²⁰ study, as Holt–Winters models are superior modeling less variable monthly flow, while SARIMA models better forecast for highly variable periods.

We made analysis of residuals through ACF and PACF of the residuals as shown in Fig. 10, and the result showed that the standardized residuals are normally distributed and white noises. Hence, the model considered is reliable.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We gratefully acknowledge the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) Center for the free use of ground-level ozone data.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Abebaw Bizuneh Alemu: Formal analysis (equal); Methodology (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **U. Jaya Parakash Raju:** Methodology (equal); Supervision (equal). **Abdu Mohammed Seid:** Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Bayile Damtie:** Supervision (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts, at <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/satellite-ozone>.

REFERENCES

- W. C. Adams, “Effects of ozone exposure at ambient air pollution episode levels on exercise performance,” *Sports Med.* **4**, 395–424 (1987).
- S. C. Anenberg, L. W. Horowitz, D. Q. Tong, and J. J. West, “An estimate of the global burden of anthropogenic ozone and fine particulate matter on premature human mortality using atmospheric modeling,” *Environ. Health Perspect.* **118**, 1189–1195 (2010).
- M. Jerrett, R. T. Burnett, C. A. Pope III, K. Ito, G. Thurston, D. Krewski, Y. Shi, E. Calle, and M. Thun, “Long-term ozone exposure and mortality,” *N. Engl. J. Med.* **360**, 1085–1095 (2009).
- J. M. McGrath, A. M. Betzelberger, S. Wang, E. Shook, X.-G. Zhu, S. P. Long, and E. A. Ainsworth, “An analysis of ozone damage to historical maize and soybean yields in the United States,” *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **112**, 14390–14395 (2015).
- T. Wang, L. Xue, P. Brimblecombe, Y. F. Lam, and L. Li, “Ozone pollution in China: A review of concentrations, meteorological influences, chemical precursors, and effects,” *Sci. Total Environ.* **575**, 1582–1596 (2017).
- J. Cao, J. Zhu, Q. Zeng, C. Li *et al.*, “Research advance in the effect of elevated o₃ on characteristics of photosynthesis,” *J. Biol.* **29**, 66–70 (2012).
- W. L. Chameides, P. S. Kasibhatla, J. Yienger, and H. Levy, “Growth of continental-scale metro-agro-plexes, regional ozone pollution, and world food production,” *Science* **264**, 74–77 (1994).
- Z. Feng, E. Hu, X. Wang, L. Jiang, and X. Liu, “Ground-level O₃ pollution and its impacts on food crops in China: A review,” *Environ. Pollut.* **199**, 42–48 (2015).
- A. S. Lefohn, C. S. Malley, H. Simon, B. Wells, X. Xu, L. Zhang, and T. Wang, “Responses of human health and vegetation exposure metrics to changes in ozone concentration distributions in the European Union, United States, and China,” *Atmos. Environ.* **152**, 123–145 (2017).
- G. Chattopadhyay and S. Chattopadhyay, “Univariate approach to the monthly total ozone time series over Kolkata, India: Autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) and autoregressive neural network (AR-NN) models,” *Int. J. Remote Sens.* **31**, 575–583 (2010).
- A. B. Alemu, A. M. Seid, B. D. Yeshita, and J. P. Raju, “The spatiotemporal variations of total column ozone concentration over Ethiopia,” *Res. Square* (published online, 2023).
- D. C. Carslaw, “On the changing seasonal cycles and trends of ozone at Mace Head, Ireland,” *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* **5**, 3441–3450 (2005).
- B. Cros, R. Delmas, D. Nganga, B. Clairac, and J. Fontan, “Seasonal trends of ozone in equatorial Africa: Experimental evidence of photochemical formation,” *J. Geophys. Res.: Atmos.* **93**, 8355–8366, <https://doi.org/10.1029/jd093id07p08355> (1988).
- H. Zou, “Seasonal variation and trends of TOMS ozone over Tibet,” *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **23**, 1029–1032, <https://doi.org/10.1029/96gl00767> (1996).
- G. E. P. Box and G. M. Jenkins, *Time Series Analysis: Forecasting and Control* (John Wiley & Sons, 1976).
- C. Guarnaccia, J. G. C. Breton, R. M. C. Breton, C. Tepedino, J. Quartieri, and N. E. Mastorakis, “ARIMA models application to air pollution data in Monterrey, Mexico,” *AIP Conf. Proc.* **1982**, 020041 (2018).
- K. Kumar, A. K. Yadav, M. P. Singh, H. Hassan, and V. K. Jain, “Forecasting daily maximum surface ozone concentrations in Brunei Darussalam—an ARIMA modeling approach,” *J. Air Waste Manage. Assoc.* **54**, 809–814 (2004).
- S. G. Gocheva-Ilieva, A. V. Ivanov, D. S. Voynikova, and D. T. Boyadzhiev, “Time series analysis and forecasting for air pollution in small urban area: An SARIMA and factor analysis approach,” *Stochastic Environ. Res. Risk Assess.* **28**, 1045–1060 (2014).
- A. D. Syaifei, N. Ramadhan, J. Hermana, A. Slamet, R. Boedisantoso, and A. F. Assomadi, “Application of exponential smoothing Holt Winter and ARIMA models for predicting air pollutant concentrations,” *EnvironmentAsia* **11**, 251 (2018).
- G. R. Alonso Brito, A. Rivero Villaverde, A. Lau Quan, and M. E. Ruiz Pérez, “Comparison between SARIMA and Holt–Winters models for forecasting monthly streamflow in the western region of Cuba,” *SN Appl. Sci.* **3**, 671 (2021).
- M. S. Omara and H. Kawamukaia, “Comparison between the Holt–Winters and SARIMA models in the prediction of NDVI in an Arid Region in Kenya using pixel-wise NDVI time series,” *Acad. J. Res. Sci. Publ.* **2**, 1 (2021).
- M. Markovska, A. Buchkovska, and D. Taskovski, “Comparative study of ARIMA and Holt–Winters statistical models for prediction of energy consumption,” in *XIII international conference ETAI 2016* (2016), pp. 1–6.
- A. K. Habtegebreal and A. B. Alemu, “Identification of rainfall intensity by using Bahir Dar C-band weather radar products,” *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Appl. Math.* **5**, 35–40 (2019).
- L. M. Judith, *Evaporites, Petroleum and Mineral Resources* (Elsevier, 1991).
- D. C. Montgomery, C. L. Jennings, and M. Kulahci, *Introduction to Time Series Analysis and Forecasting* (John Wiley & Sons, 2015).
- Y. R. Li, T. T. Han, J. X. Wang, W. J. Quan, D. He, R. G. Jiao, J. Wu, H. Guo, and Z. Q. Ma, “Application of ARIMA model for mid-and long-term forecasting of ozone concentration,” *Huanjing Kexue* **42**, 3118–3126 (2021).
- W. R. W. Mahiyuddin, N. I. Jamil, Z. Seman, N. I. Ahmad, N. A. Abdullah, M. T. Latif, and M. Sahani, “Forecasting ozone concentrations using Box-Jenkins ARIMA modeling in Malaysia,” *Am. J. Environ. Sci.* **14**, 118–128 (2018).

- ²⁸K. Taneja, S. Ahmad, K. Ahmad, and S. D. Attri, "Time series analysis of aerosol optical depth over New Delhi using Box–Jenkins ARIMA modeling approach," *Atmospheric Pollution Research* **7**, 585–596 (2016).
- ²⁹E. Z. Martinez, E. A. S. d. Silva, and A. L. D. Fabbro, "A SARIMA forecasting model to predict the number of cases of dengue in Campinas, State of São Paulo, Brazil," *Rev. Soc. Bras. Med. Trop.* **44**, 436–440 (2011).
- ³⁰J. D. Bermúdez, J. V. Segura, and E. Vercher, "Improving demand forecasting accuracy using nonlinear programming software," *J. Oper. Res. Soc.* **57**, 94–100 (2006).
- ³¹R. Lawton, "How should additive Holt–Winters estimates be corrected?," *Int. J. Forecast.* **14**, 393–403 (1998).
- ³²T. M. Dantas, F. L. Cyrino Oliveira, and H. M. Varela Repolho, "Air transportation demand forecast through Bagging Holt Winters methods," *J. Air Transp. Manage.* **59**, 116–123 (2017).
- ³³M. Reizer and K. Juda-Rezler, "Explaining the high PM₁₀ concentrations observed in polish urban areas," *Air Qual., Atmos. Health* **9**, 517–531 (2016).
- ³⁴H. Akaike, "Information theory and an extension of the maximum likelihood principle," in *Proceedings of the 2nd international symposium on information*, edited by B. N. Petrow and F. Czaki (Akademiai Kiado, Budapest, 1973).
- ³⁵Y. J. Puah, Y. F. Huang, K. C. Chua, and T. S. Lee, "River catchment rainfall series analysis using additive Holt–Winters method," *J. Earth Sys. Sci.* **125**, 269–283 (2016).
- ³⁶C. D. Lewis, *Industrial and Business Forecasting Methods: A Practical Guide to Exponential Smoothing and Curve Fitting* (Butterworth-Heinemann, 1982).
- ³⁷A. K. Habtegebreal, A. B. Alemu, and U. J. P. Raju, "Examining the role of quasi-biennial oscillation on rainfall patterns over Upper Blue Nile basin of Ethiopia," *AIMS Environ. Sci.* **8**, 190–203 (2021).
- ³⁸D. George and P. Mallery, *Spss for Windows Step by Step: A Simple Study Guide and Reference (10. Baski)* (Pearson Education, Inc., GEN, Boston, MA, 2010).
- ³⁹I. Dobre and A. A. Alexandru, "Modelling unemployment rate using Box-Jenkins procedure," *J. Appl. Quant. Methods* **3**, 156 (2008).
- ⁴⁰C. Tofallis, "A better measure of relative prediction accuracy for model selection and model estimation," *J. Oper. Res. Soc.* **66**, 1352–1362 (2015).
- ⁴¹I. S. Msiza, F. V. Nelwamondo, and T. Marwala, "Water demand prediction using artificial neural networks and support vector regression," *J. Comput.* **3**, 1 (2008).